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EXCIPIENT FUNCTIONALITY OF A NOVEL HYDROPHILIC BIOPOLYMER DERIVED FROM *IPOMOEA BATATAS* TUBERS

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a novel hydrophilic biopolymer derived from the tubers of *Ipomoea batatas* was evaluated. Fibre obtained after the separation of starch from the milled tubers was dried at 60 °C and pulverised. A 500 g of this was submerged in enough 3.50 % w/v sodium hypochlorite and kneaded for 10 min, washed severally with distilled water till the pH became neutral. It was submerged in sufficient 96 % v/v ethanol, stirred for 5 min, dried at 60 °C and classified with sieve 60. A 100 g of this was mixed with 250 ml of 3.0 % w/v sodium hydroxide, precipitated with acetone and dried in a desiccator. It was sized with a 250 µm sieve and coded as *I-polygel*. Its organoleptic, pH, densities, flow parameters, elemental analysis, hydration capacity, swelling index, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), moisture content/adsorption and ash profile were verified. Results show an odourless, fine, tasteless, off-white powder with pH, 6.85 ± 0.12 and mean particle size, 61.62 ± 0.2 µm. It was insoluble in organic solvents but gelled rapidly in cold water (viscosity, 1% w/v ≈ 127 cP). Moisture content/adsorption, hydration/swelling index was high. The powder displayed good flowability. It has cellulosic morphology with a melting peak of about 90 °C. Heavy metals such as lead or mercury were not detectable. The general properties of *I-polygel* show that it is a hydrophilic biopolymer and may serve as a pharmaceutical excipient for possible applications in novel drug delivery systems.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of newer excipient for drug formulations is a growing area of attention for the pharmaceutical industrial sector. This is driven by the growing need for more complex excipients and the need to ease the development of novel drug delivery systems and biotechnology-derived drugs [1].

Excipients are substances other than the pharmacologically active drug included in the formulation of a pharmaceutical dosage form [2, 3]. The reason for the inclusion of excipients alongside the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) is for ease of administration to the target patient population(s) by the intended route, improved dosing compliance, consistency and control of drug bioavailability, improved API stability, to ensure a robust and reproducible physical product, etc. [4]. Excipients commonly have a significant influence on the manufacture and quality, safety and efficacy of the API in a dosage form. It has defined functional roles in pharmaceutical dosage forms such as controlling solubility and bioavailability of the API, boosting the stability of the API in completed dosage forms, etc. [1, 3, 5].

Several pharmaceutical excipients are of natural origin, basically, plant-based. They may be produced either chemically or by other means. Some of the excipients obtained from natural sources include starch, agar, alginates, guar gum, xanthan gum, gelatin, pectin, acacia, tragacanth, cellulose, etc. Their advantages include low cost, biocompatibility, with a renewable source, eco-friendly, etc. [4, 6].

Excipients are widely used in drug delivery systems [7] and in several applications such as diluent or fillers to bulk up formulations that contain very potent active ingredients, to allow for convenient and accurate dosage (e.g. lactose, microcrystalline cellulose); disintegrants (e.g. sodium starch glycolate, croscarmellose sodium); binders (e.g. PVP, hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC)); lubricants (e.g. magnesium stearate, talc); glidants (e.g. colloidal SiO₂); polymers applicable in modified release dosage forms; protection of the API in enteric resistance dosage forms (e.g. Eudragit[®], poly(meth)acrylate); functional coating (of tablets, capsules, granules, microspheres); orodispersible tablets (ODTs) in which tablets rapidly disintegrate without chewing when placed on the tongue without the addition of water; formulation of solutions and suspensions, wetting agents (aids the dispersion of a hydrophobic API); thickening agents, etc. [4, 8]. One excipient can have different functional roles in different formulation types. For instance, lactose is widely used as a diluent, filler or bulking agent in tablets and capsules and as a carrier for dry powder inhalation products (DPIs). Furthermore, individual excipients can have different grades, types and sources depending on those different functional roles [4].

Though several excipients are of the natural origin, some of them can also be synthesised chemically or prepared semi-synthetically starting from the naturally sourced constituents. They range from simple, usually well-characterised, organic or inorganic molecules to highly complex materials that are difficult to fully characterise. Classification of excipients is based on their role in the pharmaceutical formulation, their interactions influencing drug delivery, or their chemical and physico-chemical properties [9].

Since some of the excipients are plant based [6], the agro-biomass is composed mainly of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Cellulose, the most abundant polysaccharide on earth, is a highly ordered polymer of cellobiose. Renewable resource based biopolymers such as starch and other biodegradable polymers account for around 85% of the total production capacity with synthetic biopolymers accounting for the remaining 15%. Despite the availability of biodegradable polymers, the lack of structural and functional stability prevents their commercial use. There is a strong potential for low-cost starch and cellulose based polymers for commodity applications, particularly since the monomer can be obtained from renewable agricultural resources [10].

Cellulose is an organic compound that is found in the cell wall of plants, some bacteria, and algae. It combines with lignin to provide the mechanical strength for the cell wall of plants. It is found in all the parts of many plants within our environment such as stem and bark of trees, leaves, fibrous roots, tubers etc. Cotton linters and fast growing plants are reported to be the highest sources of cellulose. Several pharmaceutical excipients with multiple applications such as microcrystalline cellulose, methylcellulose, carboxymethylcellulose, hydroxypropyl cellulose, etc. have been derived from cellulose.

Ipomoea batatas, sweet potato, of the family, Convolvulaceae, is an important vegetable and food crop grown in the tropics, subtropics and warm temperate regions of the world for its edible tubers which are rich in starch, cellulose, etc. Among the tropical tuber crops, it ranks second after cassava [11- 14]. The chemical compositions that have been identified from the storage roots are carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, organic acids, pigments, terpenes, phenolics, waxes, volatiles, vitamins, minerals, phytohormones and stress metabolites. Sweet potato is rich in carbohydrates (about 80-90% dry matter) which are made up of starch, cellulose, hemicellulose, sugars and pectin, contributing towards the dietary fibre fraction of the sweet potato roots [15, 16].

In this work, a biopolymer was developed from the fibre extracted from the tubers of *Ipomoea batatas* and its properties as a pharmaceutical excipient was investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The following materials were used as procured: sodium hydroxide (Qualikems, India), silica gel, acetone, ethanol (JHD, China), sodium hypochlorite (3.5 % w/v) (Multipro, Nigeria).

Methods

The tubers of *Ipomoea batatas* were obtained from the oil mill market, Elelenwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. It was identified in the University of Port Harcourt herbarium with a specimen voucher no: UPH/V/1263 as it was deposited.

Processing of sample

Starch was separated from the milled tubers of *Ipomoea batatas* to obtain the fibre which was dried at 60 °C and pulverised. A 500 g of this was submerged in sufficient volume of a 3.50 % w/v of sodium hypochlorite and kneaded for 10 min. It was washed severally with distilled water till the pH became neutral. It was again submerged in sufficient 96 % ethanol, stirred for 5 min, removing excess liquid, dried at 60 °C and classified with sieve 60 (Retch, Germany). A 100 g of this was mixed with 250 ml of 3.0 % w/v sodium hydroxide and precipitated with acetone. The precipitate was dried in a desiccator and reduced to 250 µm size and is referred to as the *I-polygel*.

Evaluation of the properties of *I-polygel*

The solubility profile, as well as the organoleptic characteristics of *I-polygel* was established beside other properties as detailed below.

Determination of Ash and extractive values

The total ash, acid insoluble ash, water soluble ash, ethanol and water extractive values of the *I-polygel* were verified using the methods outlined in the USP, 2007 [17] and WHO Quality control methods for herbal materials (1998) [18].

Determination of pH

The pH of 2 % w/v aqueous dispersion of the *I-polygel* was determined using a pH meter (Corning, model 10, England).

Hydration capacity

The hydration (water retention) capacity of the *I-polygel* was determined by the method of Ring [19]. A 1g quantity of the sample, y was placed in a 15ml plastic centrifuge tube and 10ml of water was added. The tube was shaken intermittently over a 2 h period and left to stand for 30 min. This was then centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 rpm. The supernatant was decanted and the weight of the powder after water uptake and centrifugation, x was determined. This was carried out in triplicate and mean values were determined, calculating the parameter from:

$$\text{Hydration capacity} = x/y \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: x is the weight of moist powder after centrifugation and y is the weight of dry powder.

Swelling index

The swelling index of the *I-polygel* was determined by modifying the methods of Bowen and Vadino, Iwuagwu and Okoli [20, 21]. The tapped volume occupied by 5g of the powder, V_x was noted. The powder was then dispersed in 85ml of water and the volume was made up to 100ml with water. After 24 hours of standing, the volume of the sediment, V_v was estimated. Triplicate determinations were carried out. The swelling index was computed as follows:

$$\text{Swelling index} = V_v/V_x \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where V_v is the volume of sediment and V_x is the tapped volume occupied by 5 g of powder.

Elemental analysis

The elemental analysis was carried out using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS), Model AA-7000, ROM version 1.01, S/N A30664700709 (Shimadzu, Japan).

Moisture content (loss on drying, LOD) and moisture sorption capacity

The moisture content of the *I-polygel* was determined using digital moisture balance (Citizen, MB-50, China). A 2 g quantity of the sample was weighed on the equipment set to heat at 105 °C. The equipment automatically switches off after about 2 min when optimum moisture contained in the sample has been removed by the heat generated from the halogen lamp. The value of moisture content was displayed in percentage.

The moisture sorption studies was carried out by storing 1.0 g of *I-polygel* in respective air-tight desiccators containing saturated aqueous solution of potassium sulphate, potassium chloride, sodium chloride and magnesium nitrate in contact with their excess solute at about 30 °C to maintain a relative humidity of 96, 84, 75 and 52 % respectively [22]. Studies lasted for 7 days. The increase in weight of the sample was calculated as percentage moisture gain as follows:

$$\% \text{ Moisture gain} = (\text{Moisture gain})/(\text{Original weight}) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) of *I-polygel*

The DSC of the *I-polygel* was carried out using a DSC equipment (Mettler Toledo; Model DSC 822, USA).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The SEM of the *I-polygel* was accomplished using a scanning electron microscope, (Phenom Prox, Phenom-World, Netherlands)

Bulk, tapped and particle densities

A 15.0 g quantity of *I-polygel* was employed in the determination of bulk and tapped densities using Stampfvolumeter (STAV 2003JEF, Germany). The particle density was determined by displacement method using a 25 ml pycnometer and *n*-hexane as a non-solvent [23]. The weight of the pycnometer (*w*) was determined (Mettler, Germany). The pycnometer was later filled with *n*-hexane and reweighed (*w*₁). The weight of *n*-hexane (*w*₂) was obtained by subtracting *w* from *w*₁. A 0.5 g (*w*₃) quantity of powder was introduced into the pycnometer containing *n*-hexane and weighed (*w*₄). The densities of the respective samples were calculated from the following equations after three replicate determinations:

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{Weight of Powder/Bulk volume} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \text{Weight of Powder/ Tapped volume} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\text{Particle Density, } \rho_t = w_3 / v(w_3 - w_4 + w_2 + w) \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Where: *v* is the volume of pycnometer, 25 ml, *W* = weight of empty pycnometer,
*W*₁ = weight of pycnometer and *n*-hexane, *W*₂ = the difference between the *W* and *W*₁
*W*₃ = weight of *I-polygel*, *W*₄ = weight of *I-polygel* + *n*-hexane + pycnometer.

Determination of flow properties

The flow rate of *I-polygel* was determined using the funnel method reported by Carstensen and Chan [24]. The time for 15.0 g of the sample placed in the funnel to freely flow out was noted. The angle of repose was determined using the method reported by Zeleznik and Renak [25]. A funnel of 60 ° wall angle and 10.0 mm orifice internal diameter was clamped to have its stem base at a fixed height of 4.0 cm. The sample was poured through the funnel until the apex of the conical heap formed touched the stem. The base diameter of the heap was measured. The angle of repose, θ was calculated after three replicate determinations from the equation:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{2h}{d} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

where *h* = the height of the heap, *d* = base diameter of the heap.

Hausner's ratio (HR) [26] of *I-polygel* was obtained as:

$$HR = \text{Tapped density/Bulk density} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Compressibility Index (CI) [27] of *I-polygel* was calculated from the formula:

$$CI = (1 - HR) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

where HR is Hausner's ratio

Porosity (ρ) of *I-polygel* powder bed was determined from the expression:

$$\rho = \left(1 - \frac{\text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \right) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (10).$$

Particle size analysis

A cascade of sieves consisting of 1000, 500, 250, 63 and 55 μm stainless sieves (Retch, Germany) arranged in descending order of aperture size was mounted on a mechanical shaker (Retch, Germany). A 100 g of the *I-polygel* was placed on the topmost sieve and the setup was operated for 5 min. The amount of powder retained in each sieve was determined. The mean particle diameter was calculated from the equation:

$$\text{Mean particle diameter} = \Sigma (\% \text{ retained} \times \text{mean aperture}) / 100 \dots\dots\dots 11$$

Determination of the viscosity of 1.0 % w/v aqueous dispersion of *I-polygel*

A triplicate determination of the viscosity of 1.0 % w/v aqueous dispersion of *I-polygel* was determined using an Ostwald's U-tube viscometer. The viscosities of the concentration was calculated using the formula below:

$$D1/\eta2 = \rho1t1/\rho2t2 \dots \dots \dots (12)$$

Where: D1 = viscosity of water, D2 = viscosity of *I-polygel*, $\rho1$ = true density of water, $\rho2$ = true density of *I-polygel*, t1 = time of flow of water, t2 = time of flow of *I-polygel* dispersion the sample

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of data was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics 20 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General description of the *I-polygel*

The general properties of *I-polygel* are presented in Tables 1-3. It was an odourless, fine, tasteless and off-white powder with a mean particle size of $61.62 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and had a processing yield of 58 % with a pH of 6.85 ± 0.12 . The viscosity of its 1.0 % w/v aqueous dispersion was 127 cP (Table 1). It was basically insoluble in most organic solvents but easily dispersed in water at all temperatures, resulting in a clear, colloidal solution.

In processing the material of plant origin, total ash, acid insoluble and water soluble ashes represent the ash remaining after its ignition at different stages. These parameters define the quality, authenticity and purity of the simple herbal ingredients. They are therefore significant parameters for the quantitative standardisations [28]. The total ash, in particular, utilised to evaluate the purity and quality of drugs usually consists of carbonates, phosphates, silicates, and silica, which include both physiologic ash and non-physiologic ash. A high ash value is indicative of contamination, substitution, adulteration or carelessness in preparing the crude drug for use. Acid insoluble ash indicates contamination with silica, for example, earth and sand. Water soluble ash is that part of the total ash content, which is soluble in water. It is a good indicator of the water soluble salts or a number of inorganic salts present in the material being processed [18, 29]. In this work, the values for the total, acid- insoluble and water-soluble ashes were lower than the standard limits (Table 1) [18] and is an indication that *I-polygel* was properly processed.

The extractive values are used to estimate the chemical constituents present in the crude drug and furthermore assist in the evaluation of definite constituents soluble in a particular solvent. Such extractive values provide an indication of the extent of polar, medium polar and non-polar components in the material being considered [30- 32].

Densities and flow properties of the *I-polygel*

The inter-particulate interactions influence the bulk properties of a powder and also interfere with its flow. A comparison of the bulk and tapped densities can give a measure of the relative importance of these interactions in a given powder. In free-flowing powders, the initial bulk and tapped densities will be more similar than in poor flowing powders which yield greater differences between the two values [33]. A statistical comparison of the values of the bulk and tapped densities for *I-polygel* indicated an insignificant difference, showing that the powder is free flowing ($p < 0.05$). The consideration of other flow parameters such as flow rate, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose [26, 27] show that *I-polygel* has a good flow characteristic (Table 1).

Table 1: General properties of *I-polygel*.

Parameters	Values
Yield	58%
Mean particle size	$59.09 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$
pH	6.85 ± 0.12
Total ash	$1.68 \pm 0.1 \%$
Acid insoluble ash	$1.52 \pm 0.12 \%$
Water soluble ash	$0.85 \pm 0.12 \%$
Ethanol extractive yield	$1.10 \pm 0.14 \%$
Water extractive yield	$67.00 \pm 0.13 \%$
Bulk density	$0.52 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/ml}$
Tapped density	$0.62 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/ml}$
True density	$1.42 \pm 0.06 \text{ g/ml}$
Flow rate	$7.50 \pm 0.31 \text{ g/s}$
Carr's index	$12.17 \pm 1.59 \%$
Hausner's ratio	1.14 ± 0.02
Angle of repose	$28.23 \pm 0.16^\circ$
Hydration capacity	3.35 ± 0.28
Swelling index	3.93 ± 0.19
Viscosity of 1.0 % w/v aq. dispersion	127 cP
Moisture content (Loss on drying)	$11.50 \pm 0.01 \%$

Table 2: Results of moisture adsorption studies.

Relative humidity (RH)	Value
96.00 %	36.13 ± 0.45 %
84.00 %	26.80 ± 0.17 %
75.00%	26.87 ± 0.83 %
54.00%	24.33 ± 1.52 %

Moisture content, moisture adsorption, hydration capacity and swelling index

The *I-polygel* gels easily when it comes in contact with cold water forming a translucent viscous dispersion. Its ability to absorb water quickly to form a gel is depicted from the values obtained when it was tested for swelling index, hydration capacity, moisture content (Table 1) and the moisture adsorption at different relative humidity (Table 2). Moisture adsorption was proportional to relative humidity (Fig. 1).

Elemental analysis

The results of elemental analysis are presented in Table 3. Such metals as lead or mercury were below detectable level. Other heavy metals present were all less than 0.001%. Heavy metals limit less than 0.001% was specified for microcrystalline cellulose [34].

DSC and the SEM

Figures 2 and 3 are the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) thermogram and the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrograph of *I-polygel* respectively. The thermogram in Fig. 2 shows that it has a melting peak of about 90 ° C while the SEM micrograph of *I-polygel* shows the morphology of cellulose.

FT-IR

Figure 4 represents the FT IR spectrograph of *I-polygel*. The peak at 3257.7 cm^{-1} is attributable to OH bond deformation or a CH bond stretching. This may indicate a hydrated molecule or just the carbon-hydrogen bonding of the molecules. It is also possible to assign this to a free NH bonding deformation. The peak at 2932.2 cm^{-1} is a CH- bond deformation. The peak at 2038.9 cm^{-1} is indicative of an N-H bond deformation (possibly, amino group) or a related bond. The peak at 1984.3 represents a strong deformation from a strongly bonded carbonyl carbon possibly, a carboxylic acid. The peaks 1591.0 cm^{-1} represents the olefinic double bond of C-O bonds of a possibly aromatic nucleus or linear olefins. The next peak, 1353.0 is also similar. These could be esters. The peaks from 1148 to 991.5 cm^{-1} is the fingerprint region confirming the presence of an aromatic nucleus.

Fig. 1: Bar chart for moisture adsorption studies.

Table 3: Result of elemental analysis.

Element	Value (%)
Iron	1.59×10^{-4}
Copper	6.47×10^{-6}
Zinc	2.43×10^{-4}
Lead	Below detectable limit
Nickel	1.03×10^{-5}
Potassium	1.86×10^{-4}
Sodium	5.77×10^{-4}
Calcium	9.33×10^{-4}
Manganese	3.24×10^{-6}
Mercury	Below detectable limit
Arsenic	6.77×10^{-5}
Vanadium	2.00×10^{-4}

Fig.3: Scanning Electron Micrograph of *I-polygel*.

Fig. 4: FT IR of *I-polygel*.

CONCLUSION

The functionality of a biopolymer, *I-polygel* derived from the tubers of *Ipomoea batatas* have been elucidated and is viable as a hydrophilic pharmaceutical excipient. Its pH which is close to neutral offers it an advantage for the formulation of both acidic and basic drugs. The levels of heavy metal content make it suitable for the preparation of internally used medicines. Its high moisture content, moisture adsorptivity coupled with high swelling index and hydration capacity, *I-polygel* is a good hydrophilic biopolymer and would be utilisable in the future research in novel drug deliveries especially for poorly water soluble drug molecules.

Conflict of interest

We, the authors, declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this research and its publication.

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